
Contents and Discontents of Globalization Through Prism of Political Economy

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Abstract:

Globalization has evolved into a multifaceted phenomenon over time and it involves a complex dynamics and interplay of multiple factors and stakeholders such as states, non-state actors, MNCs/ TNCs, etc. This paper attempts to explore various contours of this dynamics and assess the ramifications of this overarching phenomenon through the lens of political economy. Globalization has evolved through different phases under influence of domestic and international developments since 1st century B.C. to its present version 'Globalization 4.0'. The liberal internationalist school views globalization as an instrument of economic growth, free flow of information and ideas, technological advancement, democratization and prosperity to nations. On contrary, Marxist and critical schools have criticized capitalist model of globalization for causing inequitable growth, marginalisation of disadvantaged groups, degradation of environment and cultural homogenisation. The paper argues that policymakers need to address these inherent contradictions of this inevitable and irreversible process of globalization through policy measures that would ensure fair, inclusive and sustainable growth and development through domestic interventions coupled with international co-operation and multilateralism. Globalization has potential to become a positive force to realise people's aspirations of bringing peace and prosperity to all, if it's harnessed conscientiously.

Keywords: Globalization, Political economy, Liberalism, Marxism, Growth and Development, Inequality

Introduction:

Globalization has evolved over decades to be a massive transformative force that has significantly reshaped all the dimensions of human life, especially the political- economic life.

The liberal school of thought has presented globalization as a natural culmination of politico-economic evolution and as an instrument for economic growth & prosperity. Its proponents argue that globalization has delivered the world rapid growth, technological advancements, cultural integration and free flow of information. However, the critics expose the dark side of globalisation, which is inequitable growth, regional disparities,

cultural conflicts, environmental degradation, growth in consumerism and retreat of the welfare state.

This paper attempts to explore various contours and complexities of globalisation through the lens of political economy. After discussing the contents and discontents of globalisation, it tries to navigate through the contradictions and paradoxes of globalisation. The process of globalization being irreversible and inevitable, policymakers need to adopt systemic corrective measures to allay fears surrounding globalization and to reap maximum benefit out of it for shared prosperity and peace.

Evolution of Globalization and its

Theoretical Underpinnings:

‘Globalization’, although became a buzzword in the 21st century, its roots can be traced back to the silk roads in the 1st century BC. The connotation of the word ‘Globalization’ has evolved over centuries and today it is largely viewed as the growing interdependence and integration among the nations, markets, cultures and populations brought about by the various factors like cross-border trade, free flow of information and technology, foreign investment and movement of people.

The process of globalization that kick-started with silk roads and spice routes, gained a momentum in the 15th century with onset of the ‘Age of discovery’. However, economists like John Keynes believed that globalization in its true spirit commenced only with the first industrial revolution in the late 18th century. The evolution of globalization can be understood with the three waves of globalization. The first wave was fuelled by the industrial revolution in Europe, especially the Great Britain and the colonial rule ensured the free flow of goods from European markets to the third world in return of drain of wealth from the colonies (Dadabhai Naoroji).

The second wave of globalization began with the post WW-II economic order i.e. Bretton Woods system. This was based on the liberal internationalism theory with core principles of free trade, liberal democracy, open market, human rights and rule of law. The third wave of globalization began with the fall of the iron curtain i.e. the end of the cold war and beginning of the American hegemony. The phenomenon of globalization became truly global in this phase with virtually all the countries across the world joining WTO and unprecedented technological revolution taking place.

Today the world is witnessing Globalization 4.0, which is marked with digital revolution, rise of AI, growth of giant MNCs/TNCs, development of social media and e-commerce. Thus, the evolution of

globalization has been a gradual but steady, perpetual and increasingly pervasive phenomenon in the history of humanity.

Various schools of thoughts have attempted to decrypt the complexities of globalization through various theories, some of which have been discussed here briefly.

The liberal school of thought advocated globalization as it believed that the open market forces backed with the rule of law based liberal democratic world would promote perpetual peace and bring prosperity to all. Neoliberalism went a step ahead and called for further retreat of the state and more autonomy to the market (Friedrich Hayek, 1960).

The Marxist school of thought, although it's not against the globalization in principle, but it vehemently criticized the liberal internationalist model of globalization for it being a capitalist exploitative model writ large. The core-periphery model (John Friedmann, 1966) and the world-systems theory (Immanuel Wallerstein, 1974) exposed as to how this western-capitalist model of globalization led to the drain of wealth from the global south to the global north.

The Political Economy Approach of Globalization:

Adam Smith, the father of modern political economy, defined political economy as ‘science of statesmen willing to bring prosperity to the nation’ in his renowned book ‘The Wealth of Nations’. Being a classic liberal scholar, he was a staunch supporter of laissez faire state and he heavily criticized mercantilism. Later on, this hypothesis of Adam Smith was met with critique offered by the Marxist scholars like Friedrich Engels, who suggested that such policies would only widen the gap between the ‘haves’ and ‘have-nots’.

The political economy approach studies the phenomenon of globalization vis-à-vis role of MNCs/ TNCs, international institutions and states. The milieu of global economy has transformed with the rise of

MNCs/ TNCs, which emerged in early 2000's as a result of open market and free trade policies. Advancement in communication technology, transportation sector and free flow of capital in information further accelerated this process. The architecture of international financial governance primarily consists of the pillars of WTO, IMF and World Bank. Backed by the US hegemony, these financial institutions operate on the principles of liberal internationalism with primary objective of promoting free trade, dispute resolution through co-operation, SAPs, development assistance and soft loans along with the global financial stability. The regional FTAs further boosted the market integration and interdependence with emergence of global supply chains.

The role of state in globalization vis-à-vis the impact of globalization on nature of state has been a topic of contention and debate among the scholars. There has been visible shift in this dynamics since 1990's when there was erosion of the state sovereignty and retreat of the state in light of neoliberal policies to 2000's when there was re-emergence of the state and state-led globalization on account of developments post 9/11 terror attacks, 2001 and global financial crisis, 2008.

Contents of Globalization: Achievements and Opportunities:

Rapid Economic Growth:

Arguably the greatest accomplishment of globalization would be the unprecedented rate at which economic growth has taken place in the decades following the third wave of globalization especially. The 'Borderless World' (Kenichi Ohamae, 1990) has led to the 'globalized economy' with seamless flow of goods and services, people and investment. The biggest winner of globalization i.e. China witnessed remarkable economic growth making it a global manufacturing hub. The fruits of economic growth and development percolated down leading to upliftment of crores of population from poverty especially

in the emerging economies like India and China. Further, Bretton Woods twins contributed to the development assistance to the LDCs and boosted the global financial stability.

Enhanced International Co-operation:

The increasing economic interdependence and interconnectedness due to global supply chains has forced the nations to develop mechanism for co-operation and peaceful resolution of conflicts/ disputes and thus the role of UN and its agencies has become prominent. This has further strengthened the global governance regime and promoted a rule based international order. Numerous agreements and treaties like NPT, Paris climate accord, The Earth Summit, COVAX initiative, etc. ranging from defence and healthcare to human rights and climate change are testimony to this increased co-operation underlining need for synergised efforts.

Socio-cultural Integration and Cosmopolitanism:

Although globalization is primarily a politico-economic concept, cultural integration is an offshoot of borderless world thanks to the free flow of information, growth of social media and movement of people across the borders. The socio-cultural integration has led to the birth of 'global village' (Marshall McLuhan, 1964). Cultural exchanges, interconnectedness and hybrid identities have fostered the accommodative and cosmopolitan culture across the world.

Discontents of Globalization: Failures and Challenges:

Inequitable Growth and Development:

Although globalization delivered the economic growth at rapid pace, this growth is marked by stark inequality at international & intranational levels. The Marxist & Critical school scholars have pointed out as to how the wealth flowed from the global South to global North through a neo-colonial model of exploitation (Immanuel

Wallerstein, 1974). Further, within the Western nations, globalization benefitted the plutocrats the most further widening the 1-99 percent gap making the rich richer & poor poorer. The invisible hand has failed in many economies and 'global governance without global government' has led to undemocratic paternalism & further marginalization of the Africa especially Sub-Saharan region (Joseph Stiglitz, 2002).

Retreat of Welfare State:

The liberal internationalist model of globalization was based on the core principle of laissez faire with belief that benefits of economic growth would percolate down across all the strata of society. Neoliberalism further advocated for retreat of the state, which ultimately rendered a Welfare State into mere Police State, however this had a disproportionately adverse impact on the marginalized communities. Further the idea of free and open market, growth of MNCs/ TNCs and global governance has led to erosion of state sovereignty.

Socio-cultural Homogenisation and Westernization:

The model of globalization backed by the American hegemony inevitably had western footprints, making it de-facto instrument of Westernization and leading to erosion of indigenous cultures, traditions, dialects and identities. The inevitable ramifications of this have been the clash of civilizations (Samuel P. Huntington, 1996), cultural imperialism and loss of cultural diversity.

Climate Change and Environmental Degradation:

The capitalist model of globalization is based on consumerism that has worsened the crisis of 'limited resources, unlimited wants'. The increased greenhouse gas emissions, deforestation, exploitation of natural resources, pollution, etc. have led to global warming, climate change, ozone layer depletion, extreme weather events, desertification, etc. The disproportionately affected nations due to environmental degradation are basically the

underdeveloped/ developing countries and small island nations due to their limited adaptability & resiliency, greater vulnerability to extreme events and economic dependency on climate-sensitive sectors like agriculture/ fisheries. Lack of consensus about common but differentiated responsibility and enforcement/ finance mechanism has constrained the effectivity of global climate action.

Crisis of Globalization: Rise of Nationalism and Populism:

There is trend of growing resistance to the globalization with rise in nationalism, populism, protectionism at state level and xenophobia, anti-immigrant protests, son of the soil movements, ethnic conflicts, traditionalism at socio-political level. The anti-globalisation sentiment is on rise in not only the 'loser' countries but also the 'winner' countries of globalization (Pratap Bhanu Mehta, 2016) which is evident from the developments like rise of Trumpism and conservative parties like AfD, National Rally in Europe, which casts doubt on the future of experiment of globalization.

The Way Ahead: Addressing the Contradictions of Globalization:

Irrespective of differences of ideologies, there has been near consensus among the scholars about the irreversible and inevitable nature of globalization (Kofi Annan, 1999). Hence, there's need of synergised global efforts to harness the potential of globalization while mitigating the fear about it.

Firstly, to bridge the gap between global South and global North and to ensure equity across generations, policies promoting inclusive growth and development need to be adopted. Even the developed countries have high inequality (The Elephant Chart by Christoph Lakner and Branko Milanovic, 2013), hence affirmative action and wealth redistribution measures coupled with social security and labour welfare programs are necessary so

that the benefits of globalization are enjoyed by the marginalized communities as well.

The global governance regime is dominated by the P5 alienating interests of other countries, hence there's need of reforms to ensure democratization of the international institutions. The new international order needs to be more representative, multilateral, equitable, co-operative, accountable, democratic, rules-based, multi-polar and balanced.

Further, the pressing challenge of environmental degradation and climate change can only be tackled through global efforts and it requires sustainable development strategies. The countries have to agree upon common but differentiated responsibility principle and accordingly effectuate finance mechanism for transition to green technologies.

There's need to rethink and reinvent the role of state as well as non-state actors in light of ever evolving nature of globalization.

Conclusion:

The phenomenon of globalization has evolved in terms of its nature, magnitude and ramifications over decades and Globalization 4.0 has become a Pandora's Box today. Exploration of globalisation through prism of political economy reveals the complex facets of globalisation as it's a double-edged sword having both the challenges as well as opportunities.

The liberal internationalist model of globalization has proved to be successful in delivering rapid economic growth, promotion of democracy and human rights, boosting international co-operation, propagation of ideas, free flow of information etc. however, it's also marred by inequitable growth, regional disparities, deprivation of marginalized communities, environmental degradation, clash of cultures, cultural homogenisation and fragmentation,

democratic deficit in international governance regime, etc.

Acknowledging these challenges, reformative policy measures need to be undertaken by the states and leaders so as to realise the full potential of globalization. Democratization of institutions of global governance, strengthening multilateral institutions to foster international cooperation, inclusive growth models, sustainable development policies along with international collaborative efforts, engaging local communities in initiatives, leveraging technology responsibly to foster innovation and immigration/ refugee policies based on humanitarian values are need of the hour. The rise in anti-globalisation sentiments even in the western world implies that the future of globalisation ultimately hinges on whether it can become an instrument for fair and equitable development of all the stakeholders while balancing their interests and allaying their fears. If harnessed successfully, globalization can become a positive force to realise everyone's aspirations bringing peace and prosperity to all.

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